

ESSENTIAL OIL UTILIZED AS A NATURAL ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS AND PRESERVATIVE IN PROCESS MEAT PRODUCTS.

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Abstract: *Essential oils have gained attention as natural antimicrobial agents and preservatives in meat products, meeting the demand for minimally processed and preservative-free foods. Various essential oils, such as thyme, oregano, cinnamon, and clove, have shown antimicrobial activity against pathogens like *Listeria monocytogenes*. These essential oils can inhibit the growth of bacteria and biofilm formation, reducing the risk of contamination and extending the shelf life of meat products. Encapsulation techniques have been explored to preserve the biological activities of essential oils and minimize their effects on food sensory qualities. However, the use of essential oils in meat products may not significantly affect pH, water content, or cooking losses, but it can impart a distinctive herbal aroma and taste. Incorporating essential oils into the meat industry presents opportunities to meet consumer preferences for natural and healthier food options, but challenges such as solubility, oxidation susceptibility, and volatility need to be addressed.*

Keyword: *Essential oil, natural preservative, antimicrobial agents, sensory quality*

INTRODUCTION

Growing consumer awareness about the health risks associated with synthetic preservatives in meat products has led to a demand for natural alternatives. The use of chemical additives, such as nitrites, in processed meats has become controversial due to the potential formation of carcinogenic compounds [1]. Essential oils (EOs) derived from plants and spices have shown promise as natural preservatives for

meat products, with antimicrobial and antioxidant properties [2,3]. However, there are challenges in using EOs, such as their intense flavor and low solubility in water. Encapsulation techniques, including nanotechnological processes, have been explored to overcome these limitations and improve the effectiveness of EOs as preservatives [4]. The substitution of hazardous synthetic preservatives with natural alternatives is an ongoing issue, with challenges including data scarcity and the need for suitable assessment methods [5]. Overall, research is focused on finding safe and effective natural preservatives to meet consumer demands for healthier meat products.

Essential oils have emerged as promising natural alternatives with antimicrobial properties. They have been shown to have antimicrobial activity against various pathogens, including multiresistant pathogens such as *Candida* species [6]. Essential oils derived from native plants have been investigated for their antimicrobial and healing activities, particularly in the treatment of wound infections caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* [3,7]. Essential oils are considered as potential alternatives to industrial pharmaceutical antibiotics due to their bioactive compounds that positively affect human and animal health [8]. Furthermore, essential oils have been studied for their antimicrobial and anti-biofilm activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* strains, including methicillin-resistant strains [9]. The antimicrobial activity of essential oils is attributed to their chemical composition, which varies among different chemotypes [1,10]. Essential oils show promise as natural alternatives with antimicrobial properties, making them potential candidates for the development of new drugs or strategies for combating microbial diseases.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

2.1. Evaluate the antimicrobial Impact of different essential oils.

Different essential oils have been evaluated for their antimicrobial impact in processed meat. Thyme essential oil encapsulated into zein fibers showed antimicrobial activity against thermotolerant coliforms, *Escherichia coli*, and coagulase-positive *Staphylococcus* in meat trays under refrigeration [3,10]. The essential oil of *Salvia officinalis* (sage EO) in combination with heat treatment was effective in inactivating *Listeria monocytogenes* in beef tenderloin processed sous-vide [2]. Terpenoid-rich extracts, including essential oils obtained from various spices and medicinal herbs, have shown potential as natural antioxidants and antimicrobials to prolong the shelf-life of meat and processed meat products [3,5]. Mānuka and kānuka oils have also demonstrated antimicrobial characteristics and

the potential to be used as natural preservatives in food applications, particularly against *L. monocytogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus* in vacuum-packed beef pastes [11].

Essential oils commonly used in meat processing.

Some of the commonly used essential oils in meat processing include black pepper, caraway, *Coreopsis tinctoria* Nutt., coriander, garlic, oregano, sage, sweet basil, thyme, and winter savory [4,12]. Essential oils can be incorporated into meat products through nanotechnological processes, where they are encapsulated into a lipid or biopolymer matrix to reduce their intense flavor and improve their solubility in water [13]. Nanoemulsions of essential oils have also been developed, which have improved bioactivity and can be used as natural preservatives in meat and meat products. Essential oils offer a natural alternative to traditional preservatives and can enhance the safety, hygiene, and quality of meat and meat-based foods.

The following fragrant plants are commonly used in meat and meat-derived products: oregano, thyme, rosemary, basil, cinnamon, peppermint, clove, garlic, ginger, and sage.

2.3. Essential oils used as a preservative of processed meat products.

Essential oils have been found to have a positive impact on the shelf life of processed meat products. Thyme essential oil encapsulated into zein fibers showed antimicrobial activity against thermotolerant coliforms, *Escherichia coli*, and coagulase-positive *Staphylococcus* in meat trays under refrigeration [14]. Lemon essential oil nanoemulsion decreased the total volatile basic nitrogen content and total bacterial colony in pork patties, leading to extended storage time [15]. The essential oil of *Salvia officinalis* (sage EO) inactivated *Listeria monocytogenes* in beef tenderloin that had undergone sous-vide processing, enhancing the efficacy of heat treatment [16]. Oregano essential oil applied directly on the surface of fresh pork increased lightness and hue and decreased redness, while also providing a distinctive herbal aroma and taste [4]. Plant-derived extracts, including oregano-rosemary oil, added to pork packaged in vacuum or modified atmosphere packaging, extended shelf-life by preserving meat quality and reducing lipid oxidation [17].

The incorporation of essential oils into meat formulations and its impact on product quality.

The incorporation of essential oils into meat formulations can affect product quality in various ways. For example, the application of oregano essential oil on the

surface of fresh pork can increase lightness and hue and decrease redness, resulting in changes in meat color [1,18]. Thyme essential oil encapsulated into zein fibers can inhibit the growth of thermotolerant coliforms, *Escherichia coli*, and coagulase-positive *Staphylococcus* in meat on trays under refrigeration, making it a promising active packaging for meat products [2,9]. Lemon essential oil nanoemulsion can decrease the total volatile basic nitrogen content and total bacterial colony in pork patties, leading to extended storage time [5,8]. Plant-derived extracts, such as garlic extract and oregano-rosemary oil, added to meat packaged in vacuum or modified atmosphere packaging, can affect color variables, lipid oxidation, and shear stress, with vacuum-packed meat being more stable in terms of quality [4,13]. Incorporating rosemary essential oil nanoemulsions into *Eremurus luteus* root gum coating solution can reduce pH, TBA value, and total viable microbial count of chicken meat, while enhancing sensory parameters such as odor, color, and total acceptance [5,17].

Influence of essential oils on the sensory attributes (flavor, aroma) and overall quality of meat products.

Essential oils (EOs) have been studied for their influence on the sensory attributes and overall quality of meat products. EOs, such as lemon essential oil, oregano essential oil, and bamboo essential oil, have been found to have antimicrobial effects, reducing the total bacterial colony and inhibiting the growth of microorganisms in meat products [1,19]. The application of EOs can also enhance the flavor and aroma of meat, giving it a distinctive herbal aroma and taste [4]. Additionally, EOs have been shown to improve the oxidative stability of meat, reducing the generation of oxidative products and extending the storage time of meat products [4,20]. However, it is important to note that the intensity of the flavor of EOs can affect the sensory properties of meat, and the correct dosage and encapsulation methods need to be considered to mitigate these effects. Overall, EOs have the potential to improve the sensory attributes and overall quality of meat products while providing antimicrobial and antioxidant benefits.

Conclusion.

Essential oils (EOs) have the potential to enhance the safety and quality of meat products while meeting consumer preferences for natural and minimally processed foods. EOs and their isolated compounds (EOCs) have been found to have antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, which can help control microbial growth and extend the shelf life of meat products. The antimicrobial activity of EOs has been shown to inhibit the growth of various microorganisms, including

thermotolerant coliforms, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus*. Additionally, EOs have been found to have antioxidant capacity, which can help preserve the quality of meat products. Encapsulation techniques have been used to improve the solubility and stability of EOs, making them more suitable for use in food systems and active packaging. However, further research is needed to fully understand the mechanisms of action and potential toxicity of EOs, as well as to optimize their application in meat products.

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